

Curating Power: Open Source Infrastructures in the Service of National and Geopolitical Agendas

OpenForum Academy Symposium 2025: Open Technologies and Geopolitics
Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

18. November 2025

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Abstract

This paper examines the rise of open national digital infrastructures (DI) or “sovereign technology stacks” as instruments of geopolitical and security strategy. Across regions, states increasingly assemble layered “stacks” that integrate technology, governance, finance, and policy to project influence and advance national agendas.

Here, we introduce the concept of stack curation, defined as the intentional selection, configuration, and export of open-source components to serve geopolitical and security objectives. Even when built from ostensibly open technologies, curated stacks embed national priorities and reproduce power through infrastructural interdependencies.

Drawing on two comparative cases, China’s Gitee platform and the U.S. Government’s PEPFAR program and its DHIS2-based health information systems, the paper proposes a typology of curatorial mechanisms (selection, canonization, gatekeeping, dependence, domestication) and examines their implications for global digital governance and the evolving politics of “openness” as an instrument of sovereignty.

Introduction: “Stacks of Power”

Digital infrastructures increasingly operate as geopolitical artefacts. What began as technical architectures of interoperability are becoming critical to national, geopolitical and security agendas with competing ‘sovereign’ digital infrastructure strategies. Across regions, governments adopt open-source components yet govern them through national frameworks of security, industrial policy, and diplomacy. Here, the authors argue that stacks are layered digital infrastructures, ranging from physical networks and hardware, through operating systems and code sharing platforms, to norms and standards, that are “curated” to serve geopolitical agendas and national security strategies.

This paper define it as the practice by which states or institutions select, integrate, and maintain digital components to assert political and strategic objectives. This concept helps explain how open-source ecosystems are folded into national governance and foreign-policy agendas.

This paper asks:

1. How do states and funders curate open-source infrastructures into sovereign technology stacks?
2. Through which mechanisms—selection, canonization, gatekeeping, patronage, domestication—is infrastructural power exercised?
3. How does such governance externalities result for the open-source community and its adopters?

To explore these questions, this paper examine two contrasting cases: China’s Gitee, where open source is domesticated under regulatory enclosure, and PEPFAR’s DHIS2 stack, where openness is institutionalised through donor governance. These examples illustrate how “openness” can be curated, with a full-four freedom yet politically constrained.

From free to sovereign: the epistemic loading of technology stacks

The term “technology stack” originally describes layers of computing architecture, e.g. in software development. Following a model set by India through their set of modular components for government-citizen interaction (IndiaStack), it has also come to signify layered interoperable digital public infrastructure (DPI)¹. In this capacity, it has been used as a concept to frame digital geopolitical agendas².

This novel, broader understanding reflects a broader sociotechnical shift, where digital infrastructure is understood to encompass not only technologies themselves but guidance, funding, governance mechanisms, and other aspects relevant for deployment and sustained usage. Term usage in policy discourse has surged in the context of debates about digital sovereignty, invigorated by Chinese digital foreign policy, such as the Digital Silk Road (DSR) initiative, US-China-EU multipolarity, and US tech-protectionism.

Figure 2 (below) illustrates the evolution of the term “stack” from a technical to a geopolitical construct.

Geopolitical shifts have elevated such infrastructure as a key component of “digital sovereignty”, broadly defined as a state’s ability to exercise power and control over ‘the digital’.³ This broader understanding signals a shift from technical architecture to sociotechnical governance. Digital infrastructure now encompasses not only code and hardware but also guidance, funding, governance mechanisms, and other aspects relevant for deployment and sustained usage.

¹ Panday, Jyoti. *India Stack: Public-Private Roads to Data Sovereignty*. Atlanta, GA: Internet Governance Project, 2023. https://www.internetgovernance.org/wp-content/uploads/India_stack_9_1_2023.pdf, starting with Unique ID Authority of India (UIDAI) Aadhaar project ‘India Stack’, accessed 9 April 2025, <https://indiastack.org/>.

² Figure 1 in the Appendix compares national stacks according to diverging components, funding mechanisms, and so forth.

³ Weizenbaum Institute. (n.d.). *Digital sovereignty*. Retrieved April 9, 2025, from <https://fundamentals.weizenbaum-institut.de/en/digital-sovereignty>

Governments and supranational organisations invoke ‘digital sovereignty’ to justify control over each layer of their digital stack, from semiconductors and physical networks (physical layer) to software and data (code and data layers).⁴ As a result, the global technology landscape is becoming increasingly fragmented from a geopolitical perspective. Arguably, the stack is becoming a normative and strategic tool by providing a blueprint for state-led efforts to assert control over digital infrastructure and governance.⁵ However, key national differences exist between models of DPI: while the EU emphasises sovereignty through openness,⁶ the US emphasises security through openness and so forth.

These stacks comprise different core technologies, funding and governance mechanisms and commitments to open source ideas, as outlined in Table 1 in the Appendix. When infrastructural technologies or even entire stacks are exported by serving as a blueprint for other countries, e.g. IndiaStack, they double as soft power and foreign policy tools.

Open Source Infrastructures: Serving a Purpose?

In recent years, open source has transitioned from a model of software freedom to a strategic mechanism for states and institutions to reclaim control—particularly from large technology providers headquartered in foreign jurisdictions. In the European context, this evolution aligns with the discursive rise of “digital sovereignty” as part of the ambition to reduce or remove dependence on non European cloud and platform providers⁷ and reclaim sovereignty over critical infrastructure and data.

This shift unfolds across three overlapping discursive framings for open source:⁸

⁴ Francesca Bria et al., *EuroStack – A European Alternative for Digital Sovereignty* (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2025), 127 p., 127 p., <https://www.bertelsmann-stiftung.de/doi/10.11586/2025006>.

⁵ MCTD, *A Humanitarian Perspective on Digital (Public) Infrastructure* (Minderoo Centre for Technology and Democracy, Forthcoming).

⁶ Roberts, H., Cowls, J., Casolari, F., Morley, J., Taddeo, M., & Floridi, L. (2021). *Safeguarding European values with digital sovereignty: An analysis of statements and policies*. *Internet Policy Review*, 10(3).

⁷ Pohle, J., & Thiel, T. (2021). *Digital sovereignty*. In B. Herlo, D. Irrgang, G. Joost, & A. Unteidig (Eds.), *Practicing Sovereignty: Digital Involvement in Times of Crises* (pp. 47–69). Bielefeld: Transcript-Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783839457603-003>.

⁸ Bratton, B. H. (2016). *The Stack: On Software and Sovereignty*. MIT Press; Bertelsmann Stiftung. (2025, February 13). *EuroStack – A European Alternative for Digital Sovereignty*. <https://www.bertelsmann-stiftung.de/en/our-projects/reframetech-algorithmen-fuers-gemeinwohl/project-news/eurostack-a-european-alternative-for-digital-sovereignty>; OpenForum Europe. (2022). *Software Public Organizations as Civic Infrastructure*. OpenForum Europe. <https://openforumeurope.org/publications/software-public-organisations-as-civic-infrastructure/>; European Commission. (2020). *Open Source Software Strategy 2020–2023: Think Open*. Publications Office of the European Union. https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/organisational-structure/open-source-software-strategy_en.

Open source as free

The 2010-2020s sees the formalization of open source largely through a discourse of ‘free to use’ in EU policy – e.g. EU’s Open Source Software Strategy (2020-2023) and open source as civic infrastructure (OpenForum Europe 2022).

Open source as critical infrastructure

Security crises are key discursive turning points, which led to governments elevating open source to critical infrastructure (e.g. CRA in EU) through funding and accountability mechanics.

Open source as sovereign

The narrative of ‘sovereign’ emerges as layered governance combining hardware and compute with law and regulation. This framing emphasizes that states must control enough of each to maintain national autonomy. The place of open source is ambiguous and malleable, initially signifying openness and collaboration and by the 2020s, signifying privatization.

Curatorial Practices of Open Source

This article puts forward the concept of ‘stack curation’. Situated within STS, it is defined as the set practices by which state institutions assemble and legitimize the layers of a *sovereign technology stack*—the combination of software, standards and policies that underlie national DPI.⁹ This concept offers a means for understanding how states operationalize open source ecosystems into governable infrastructures, typified by weaponized interdependence.¹⁰ Curation, in this sense, is a political and organisational act. It encompasses selection, integration, maintenance, and governance of open components within institutional frameworks, transforming distributed public code into governable infrastructure.

Building on the infrastructural turn in STS and scholarship on algorithmic curation,¹¹ the authors view power as working through circulations of standardisation.¹² Curation stabilises what counts as legitimate, secure,

⁹ Star, S. L., & Ruhleder, K. (1996). Steps toward an ecology of infrastructure: Design and access for large information spaces. *Information Systems Research*, 7(1), 111–134.

<https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.7.1.111>; Jasanoff, S. (Ed.). (2004). *States of knowledge: The co-production of science and social order*. Routledge.

¹⁰ Farrell, H., & Newman, A. L. (2019). Weaponized interdependence: How global economic networks shape state coercion. *International Security*, 44(1), 42–79. https://doi.org/10.1162/isec_a_00351

¹¹ This includes literature on infrastructural power (Mann, 1984), infrastructural ideology (Maxigas, 2023), algorithmic curation (Gillespie 2018), etc.

¹² Collier, S.J. & Lakoff, A. (2009) On vital systems security. *International Political Sociology*, 3(1), p.2–17: Bowker, G.C. and Star, S.L. (1999) *Sorting Things Out: Classification and Its Consequences*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

or sovereign infrastructure. Stack curation is relational. It coordinates interfaces across layers, aligns them with regulatory requirements and embeds interdependencies across layers. This process, we argue, is highly sociotechnical and not just technical.¹³

Curation manifests across multiple mechanisms, including:

- Selection of aligned components and repositories.
- Forking or modification of open-source projects.
- Centralised standard-setting (e.g. Gaia-X, EU CRA).
- Strategic financing and ODA channels (e.g. DSR, MDB-funded DPIs).
- Supply-chain governance and export controls (e.g. EAR restrictions on cryptographic tools).

Within open source stack curation, we see diverging policies that normatively emphasise generativity versus control (tight curation versus open curation) and sovereignty versus interdependence (forkable for autonomy, yet interoperable for collaboration, e.g. open standards). On the one hand, we have traditional 'hard control' on technology ranging from export/import control: FOSS (Office of Foreign Asset Control) to softer forms of control, such as public private partnership (NIST Minimum Security Requirements).

Below is a typology for how 'curation' operates within national technology stacks is developing. The curation typology reveals how openness can be systematically configured into governance and control.

Figure 3: Typology of "Curation" in National Tech Stacks

Modality	Dimensions	Mechanism	Examples
Curatorial selection	Epistemic / Technical	Selecting 'aligned' components or repositories (can be OS, libraries etc.)	OS China's domestication of existing open-source projects(Harmony OS etc.)
Curatorial framing	Discursive / Narrative	Rebranding and communication of (national)open technology stacks as "sovereign," "secure," or "open," embedding normative claims about autonomy and trust.	Gaia-X as "sovereign cloud" (EU); EuroStack as "European digital infrastructure"; China's Digital Silk Road as a model of "open cooperation."
Curatorial canonization	Normative/ standard setting	Institutionalising specific architectures or reference designs as de facto standards through replication, toolkits, and policy endorsement.	IndiaStack as reference for digital identity systems globally; Estonia's X-Road model
Curatorial dependence	Structural/ Technical	Long-term maintenance, dependency management, lifecycle governance of core stack components	U.S. and EU investments in "critical OSS" supply chains(Sovereign Tech Agency, NIST); GitHub's dependency

¹³ Jasanoff, S., & Kim, S.-H. (2009). *Containing the atom: Sociotechnical imaginaries and nuclear power in the United States and South Korea*. *Minerva*, 47(2), 119–146. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-009-9124-4>.

			security programmes ¹⁴ ; government-funded OSS stewards (OpenSSF).
Gatekeeping (Curatorial controls)	Institutional / Political	Regulation of participation, contribution, and forking rights; defining who can shape standards or access the infrastructure	Huawei–Linux Foundation membership controversies; export controls on cryptographic ¹⁵ FOSS tools under the U.S. EAR ¹⁶ (i.e., Python is EC003 under ECCN).
Curatorial Patronage	Financial / Strategic	Direct or indirect financing of specific infrastructures to advance national or donor agendas; linking aid, loans, or trade to adoption of certain stacks.	Official Development Assistance (ODA) for DPIs by MBB; China’s Digital Silk Road investments; USG’s support for DHIS2 adoption
Curatorial Domestication	Regulatory / Infrastructural	Forking or replicating global open-source projects within national boundaries to ensure jurisdictional control and compliance.	Gitee as China’s domesticated alternative to GitHub; open-source forks such as Redis→Valkey (Amazon) or Terraform→OpenTofu (Linux Foundation) or Hashicorp Vault → Open Bao

While it may seem that states and funders transform open-source ecosystems into curated infrastructures of governance by blurring the line between collaboration and control, autonomy and dependency. The reality is that in OSS landscape, curation practice can operate bidirectionally:

Top-down, through government mandates, export controls, and funding channels that formalise control.

Bottom-up, as communities resist instrumentalisation—for instance, the NixOS community’s debate over defence-industry sponsorship (Anduril, 2024), reflecting contestation within FOSS governance itself.

¹⁴Crosby, K., & Cochran, G. (2025, August 11). *Securing the supply chain at scale: Starting with 71 important open source projects*. GitHub Blog. <https://github.blog/open-source/maintainers/securing-the-supply-chain-at-scale-starting-with-71-important-open-source-projects/>

¹⁵ Bureau of Industry and Security. (2023). Technical Note 1. In [Title of document: CCL5 Pt.2-4]. U.S. Department of Commerce. Retrieved from <https://www.bis.doc.gov/index.php/documents/regulations-docs/2337-ccl5-pt2-4/file>

¹⁶ Bureau of Industry and Security. (2023, November 17). *List of items controlled – Section A ‘Technology’, Category 5 – Part 2 (Information Security)*. In *Export Administration Regulations, Supplement No. 1 to Part 774*. U.S. Department of Commerce. <https://www.bis.doc.gov/index.php/documents/regulations-docs/2337-ccl5-pt2-4/file>

Case Study: Gitee

Background and Context:

Since its launch in 2013, Gitee(码云) has been promoted as the official national platform for open-source software hosting and collaboration, supported by the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology (MIIT) as part of a broader policy to build indigenous software ecosystems, namely a “Chinese alternative” to GitHub¹⁷. Gitee evolved as a commercial, centrally managed platform within China’s digital ecosystem, offering Git and SVN repository hosting, now AI, all tightly integrated with OSChina’s web development community¹⁸.

By contrast, Gitea is an independent, community-driven open-source project, emerged in 2016 as a fork of Gogs after contributors sought to overcome the limits of single-maintainer governance. Gitea introduced a distributed development model and released version 1.0 in December 2016, becoming one of the most widely adopted self-hosted Git services for open-source communities and public institutions. Released under the MIT License, Gitea adopted a distributed model of open collaboration and quickly became one of the world’s most widely deployed self-hosted Git services. Despite having no technical or institutional connection, the two platforms embody a semiotic convergence: the adoption of open-source language, aesthetics, and culture into the apparatus of sovereign digital control.

Within China’s digital-governance strategy, Gitee is not simply a hosting service but an instrument of industrial and ideological policy. It forms part of a broader constellation of national platforms—including KylinOS, HarmonyOS, and the China Software Industry Association’s open-source working groups—that advance the state’s vision of technological self-reliance and secure, controllable infrastructure. Under the Cybersecurity Law (2017), Data Security Law (2021), and Cybersecurity Review Measures (2021), platforms deemed “critical to national data security” fall under heightened state oversight. Gitee’s operations thus sit at the intersection of open collaboration and national security governance.

In May 2022, Gitee announced that all publicly hosted repositories would be temporarily made private pending manual review of all code submissions, a measure framed as an “improvement to content review procedures¹⁹” which is in alignment with China’s Cybersecurity Review Measures, which extend state jurisdiction to digital infrastructure deemed critical to national data security.

¹⁷ Liao, R. (2020, August 21). China is building a GitHub alternative called Gitee. TechCrunch. <https://techcrunch.com/2020/08/21/china-is-building-its-github-alternative-gitee>

¹⁸ Gitee. “About Us.” Accessed April 9, 2025. <https://gitee.com/about-us>.

¹⁹ Creemers, R., & Webster, G. (2022, January 10). Translation: Cybersecurity Review Measures (Revised) – Effective Feb. 15, 2022 [Translation of 《网络安全审查办法》]. DigiChina, Stanford University. <https://digichina.stanford.edu/work/translation-cybersecurity-review-measures-revised-effective-feb-15-2022/> translated from 中央网络安全和信息化委员会办公室; 国家互联网信息办公室; 国家发展和改革委员会; 工业和信息化部; 公安部; 国家安全部; 财政部; 商务部; 中国人民银行; 国家市场监督管理总局; 国家广播电视总局; 中国证券监督管理委员会; 国家保密局; 国家密码管理局. (2022, January 4). *网络安全审查办法* [Decree No. 8]. http://www.cac.gov.cn/2022-01/04/c_1642894602182845.htm

Curatorial Modalities in the Gitee Ecosystem:

Gitee exemplifies several of the curatorial modalities outlined in the typology:

- **Curatorial Selection:** MIT's endorsement designates Gitee as the trusted repository for national projects, effectively defining the boundaries of legitimate software collaboration within China's open-source ecosystem.
- **Curatorial Domestication:** Gitee localises global open-source practices under national jurisdiction, aligning them with state priorities for "secure and controllable" infrastructure.
- **Curatorial Framing:** Official narratives of 自主可控 ("self-controlled and independent") recast where open source is a patriotic and sovereign endeavour rather than a transnational commons.

Case Study: Curating Openness through Development Aid

Background and Context

The U.S. President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR) is one of the most data-intensive global health programs in the world²⁰, operating across more than fifty countries and responsible for over 110 billion USD²¹ in investments since 2003²². PEPFAR's architecture has, from the beginning, rested on an indicator-based performance logic, treating data as a strategic asset. Its Data Governance Framework (2017)²³ defines the purpose and scope of data management, anchors it in U.S. federal policy²⁴, and institutionalizes governance under the Office of the Global AIDS Coordinator.

Within this ecosystem, data systems such as the PEPFAR Data Hub (PDH)²⁵, FACTS Info²⁶, Panorama/Spotlight (for public data visualization and analysis)²⁷, and the Data for Accountability, Transparency and Impact Monitoring (DATIM) platform²⁸ form an ecosystem that architects PEPFAR's data-as-asset²⁹ a profound faith in the capacity of data and evidence to generate solutions that could, in its own vision, "finally end the AIDS epidemic³⁰."

DHIS2 is widely recognized as a core component (or "core stack") within the broader digital architecture that enables PEPFAR's data-driven decision making and international development work. DHIS2, developed by the Health Information Systems Programme (HISP) at the University of Oslo, is the world's largest open-source health information platform, used by Ministries of Health in more than 80 countries for

²⁰ U.S. President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR). (2017, August 9). PEPFAR Data Governance [PDF]. https://learn.pepfar.net/assets/courseware/v1/e09bc70ae756515f14e096aa033628f2/asset-v1%3Alearn-pepfar-net+PMDATVW_1+2018_9+type%40asset+block/20170809_PEPFAR_Data_Governance.pdf

²¹ The Lancet HIV. (2023, August 17). PEPFAR reauthorisation hangs in the balance [Editorial, 10(9), e557]. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-3018\(23\)00205-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-3018(23)00205-9)

²² Congressional Research Service. (2012, October 10). The President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR): Funding issues after a decade of implementation, FY2004–FY2013 (CRS Report No. R42776). [https://www.congress.gov/crs_external_products/R/PDF/R42776/R42776.5.pdf]

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Office of Management and Budget. (2016, July 28). OMB Circular A-130: Managing Information as a Strategic Resource (Revision) [Circular]. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/a130revised.pdf>

²⁵ The central aggregation and management system for program data

²⁶ Serves as the official record for annual local funding, tracking approved Country Operational Plan (COP) and budget allocations.

²⁷ The primary public-facing business intelligence platform for making PEPFAR program data available and visualizing results

²⁸ A platform for monitoring and evaluation, designed to facilitate real-time tracking and reporting across PEPFAR partner countries

²⁹ Kalie, D., Knight, C., Avery, L., White, L. A., Bonanno, L., ... Raulfs-Wang, E. C. (2023). Midpoint reflections on USAID HIV local partner transition efforts. *Global Health: Science and Practice*, 11(3), e2200338. <https://doi.org/10.9745/GHSP-D-22-00338>

³⁰ Rhodes T. Sustaining policy promise: rhetorics of disease elimination and sustainable development. *Medical Humanities* Published Online First: 30 July 2025. doi: 10.1136/medhum-2025-013245

health management, disease surveillance, and logistics data. Its open, modular design, capacity for local configuration³¹. PEPFAR-supported countries and implementing partners frequently leverage DHIS2 for national and subnational HIV program data management, reporting, and analysis^{32 33}.

Curation of Open Source as infrastructure of Funder Governance

The integration between DHIS2 and PEPFAR operates on both technical and institutional levels. Most importantly, PEPFAR's DATIM platform (a DHIS2-based system) is used for MER (Monitoring, Evaluation and Research) indicator reporting as per Data Governance Framework on recipient reporting responsibilities PEPFAR calendar by implementing partners and government counterparts. The platform enables PEPFAR to collect, analyze, and visualize data within a unified architecture that supports its performance frameworks and funding accountability mechanisms.

The integration between DHIS2 and PEPFAR operates across both technical and institutional layers. PEPFAR's Data for Accountability, Transparency and Impact Monitoring (DATIM) platform is built on the DHIS2 framework³⁴ serves as the mandatory system for reporting Monitoring, Evaluation, and Research (MER) indicators by implementing partners and government counterparts, in accordance with PEPFAR's Data Governance Framework³⁵ and annual reporting calendar³⁶. Through DATIM, implementing partners are required to submit quarterly MER results, which are reviewed during Country Operational Plan (COP) and Regional Operational Plan (ROP) processes to inform performance assessments, target-setting, and subsequent funding allocations³⁷. This integration enables PEPFAR to monitor program data within a single architecture that anchors its partners' performance management and financial accountability mechanisms.

While the open-source code remains intact, the DHIS2's deployment in PEPFAR contexts is heavily parameterized by donor-defined indicators, data standards, and governance cycles. The resulting infrastructure is technically open yet institutionally enclosed, governed by donor-driven reporting, validation, and funding rhythms. The hybrid nature of this curation offers practical benefits, including accelerated deployments including for further pandemic response including ebola³⁸ and Covid-19³⁹ and enhanced interoperability among PEPFAR-funded programs, national HMIS systems, and global surveillance tools⁴⁰. However, this creates structural tensions as well.

³¹ Shuaib F, Garba AB, Meribole E, Obasi S, Sule A, Nnadi C, et al. Implementing the routine immunisation data module and dashboard of DHIS2 in Nigeria, 2014–2019. *BMJ Global Health*. 2020;5:e002203. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2019-002203>

³² MEASURE Evaluation. (2019, September). Using DHIS2 software to track prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV: Guidance (Version 2) (MS-18-127) [PDF]. https://www.measureevaluation.org/resources/publications/ms-18-127/at_download/document

³³ Population Services International (PSI). (2021, June 18). Using DHIS2 to power PEPFAR HIV and SRH programs in Central America & the Caribbean. DHIS2. <https://www.dhis2.org/psi-lac-hiv-srh/>

³⁴ DATIM. (2025, April 28). DATIM MER metadata. Retrieved from <https://help.datim.org/hc/en-us/articles/360037706811-DATIM-MER-Metadata>

³⁵ U.S. President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR). (2017, August 9). PEPFAR Data Governance [PDF]. https://learn.pepfar.net/assets/courseware/v1/e09bc70ae756515f14e096aa033628f2/asset-v1%3Alearn-pepfar-net+PMDATVW_1+2018_9+type%40asset+block/20170809_PEPFAR_Data_Governance.pdf

³⁶ White, L. A., Avery, L., Bonanno, L., Knight, C., Irwin, C., Hoeflich, K., Kaliel, D., Hijazi, M., & Raulfs-Wang, E. C. (2023). An Evaluation of Local Implementing Partner Performance During the First 2 Years of the USAID/PEPFAR Transition. *Global health, science and practice*, 11(3), e2200337. <https://doi.org/10.9745/GHSP-D-22-00337>

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Eggers, C., Martel, L., Dismer, A., Kallay, R., Sayre, D., Choi, M., Corvil, S., Kaba, A., Keita, B., Diallo, L., Balde, M. M., Bah, M., Camara, S. M., Koivogui, E., Montgomery, J., & Keita, S. (2022). Implementing a DHIS2 Ebola virus disease module during the 2021 Guinea Ebola outbreak. *BMJ global health*, 7(5), e009240. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2022-009240>

³⁹ Mirza, M., Grant-Greene, Y., Valles, M., Joseph, P., Juin, S., Brice, S....Rosen, D. H. (2022). Leveraging PEPFAR-Supported Health Information Systems for COVID-19 Pandemic Response. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 28(13), 49-58. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2813.220751>.

⁴⁰ Kinkade, C., Russpatrick, S., Potter, R., Saebø, J., Sloan, M., Odongo, G....Gallagher, K. (2022). Extending and Strengthening Routine DHIS2 Surveillance Systems for COVID-19 Responses in Sierra Leone, Sri Lanka, and Uganda. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 28(13), 42-48. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2813.220711>.

PEPFAR's reporting indicator-centric architecture creates a form of "indicator gravity"⁴¹, pulling data from the national health information systems toward donor-defined metrics and performance frameworks. This alignment often entrenches technical and financial dependency, as structural and fiscal constraints limit the transition to nationally owned health systems and shape planning around funder priorities rather than local needs. Routing national health data through donor-managed infrastructures—such as DATIM and the PEPFAR Data Hub—further raises concerns about data sovereignty⁴², ownership, and control as well. Sustainability risks also emerge when donor-driven customizations outpace local technical and institutional capacity⁴³, making system maintenance and adaptation difficult once external funding declines.

The curatorial modalities of PEPFAR-DHIS2:

Curatorial Selection: PEPFAR's decision to anchor its data governance model in DHIS2 selectively elevates one open-source platform as the legitimate infrastructure for donor-funded programs shaping national technology choices across supported countries.

Curatorial Canonization: Through heavy investment DHIS2 becomes institutionalized as a "reference architecture" for digital health, reproduced in other public health responses and programs.

Curatorial Dependence: By synchronizing national reporting with donor-controlled systems such as DATIM and the PDH, PEPFAR embeds technical and financial dependencies that link continued data submission to eligibility for future funding.

In this case, open-source software serves both as an enabler and a medium of control. Openness becomes a governed condition, where through a curated infrastructure development funding and funder's priority circulate.

Discussion: Two stacks curation

The Gitee and PEPFAR–DHIS2 cases illustrate two distinct yet converging logics of stack curation. In China, curation operates through sovereign enclosure, the domestication and regulatory governance of open-source infrastructures to secure jurisdictional control and ideological alignment. In PEPFAR, curation is enacted through institutional governance—the embedding of open systems within donor-defined indicators, reporting cycles, and funding conditionalities.

Despite their differing orientations—state-led versus donor-led—both cases reveal how openness becomes a governed condition. Each transforms open-source infrastructures into instruments of political rationality: one through national security and industrial policy, the other through global health accountability and performance management. In both, openness functions less as an end state and more as a vector of control and interdependence. Together, these cases demonstrate that the politics of open infrastructure lie not in the code itself, but in the curatorial regimes that define its circulation, compliance, and legitimacy.

⁴¹ Wiyeh A, Komba P, Ojong SA, Wiysonge CS, Moki-Suh B, Sadate-Ngatchou P, et al. (2025) A Critical juncture in global health: Leveraging historical institutionalism to examine PEPFAR dependency and inform the development of self-reliant public health systems. *PLOS Global Public Health* 5(4): e0004440. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0004440>

⁴² Sekalala S, Chatikobo T. Colonialism in the new digital health agenda. *BMJ Global Health*. 2024;9:e014131. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2023-014131>

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Looking forward, recognizing curation as a governance paradigm invites both analytical and normative reflection. For scholars, it highlights the need to trace how openness travels—technically, discursively, and institutionally—across jurisdictions and sectors.

Conclusion

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Appendix

Figure 1: National stack comparison

	Components	Funding	Governance	Open Source	Territorial scope	DPI or national agenda
IndiaStack	ID (Aadhaar), Payments (UPI), data exchange (DEPA)	Indian Government	Sovereignty-centric ⁴⁴ , led by the Indian government	Mixed (Open APIs, DPGs and proprietary components)	Primarily India; Expansion to the Global South ⁴⁵	National digital transformation; Export model / soft power ⁴⁶
GovStack	“Building blocks” for governments to implement DPIs	Development: ODA (Germany’s BMZ) ⁴⁷ ; Implementation MDBs	Multi-stakeholder	Committed to Open Source standards & interoperability	Global but focused on developing countries	Multi-stakeholder DPI initiative.
EuroStack	Broad digital ecosystem approach & concrete DPI	Multiple sources	Rooted in digital commons; multi-stakeholder steering committee	Committed to Open Source standards & interoperability	European Union; Global through standards (‘Brussels Effect’)	Multilateral agenda for establishing EU digital sovereignty and tech leadership

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AfricaStack ⁴⁸	De facto: ID (MOSIP), Payments (MobilePay); Broad continental digital ecosystem	E.g. for ID: Multilateral agencies, global non-governmental organisations and foreign donors ⁴⁹	Fragmented, e.g. African Union, SmartAfrica initiative	Mixed	African continent	Informal multilateral agenda to establish African digital sovereignty & regional integration for economic benefit
China DSR	“Full” stack, ranging from low-level DI (5G connectivity, data centres) through IoT and AI applications	State investment banks (e.g. CDB), MDBs (AIIB), and commercial investment	Bilateral and multilateral agreements; standards setting	Increasing (DeepSeek)	Global	National agenda; part of the broader Belt and Road Initiative (
US Big Tech	“Full” stack	Venture capital & Private equity; commercial investment	Corporate governance; local legislation	Essential (baseline technologies, e.g. Linux & emerging projects, e.g. Android)	Global	Commercial agenda; national security interest

⁴⁸ While there is no official ‘AfricaStack’, the idea has recently been floated in policy circles as an exercise in increasing digital sovereignty, e.g. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. (2025, February). *Digital public infrastructure: A practical approach for Africa*. <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2025/02/digital-public-infrastructure-a-practical-approach-for-africa?lang=en>

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